

AN ITALIAN GAZE ON COLONIAL INDIA: AN ANALYSIS OF GUIDO GOZZANO'S *VERSO LA CUNA DEL MONDO*

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Abstract

*This article examines Guido Gustavo Gozzano's travelogue *Verso la cuna del mondo: Lettere dall'India* (1917) [Towards the Cradle of the World: Letters from India], a series of reflections on India written during his journey to India. Unlike many European travel writers, Gozzano was neither a colonizer nor a professional ethnographer, but an Italian poet associated with the *Crepuscolari* movement. His observations offer a distinctive Italian perspective on British India, blending direct impressions with heavy reliance on European literary sources. The article analyzes his Eurocentric gaze, his ambivalent view of colonialism, and the tension between imagination and lived experience in his depiction of India. Ultimately, Gozzano's travelogue exemplifies the way early twentieth-century Italian writing both reproduced Orientalist stereotypes and contributed to the literary construction of India in Europe.*

Keywords: *Guido Gozzano, travel writing, Orientalism, colonial India, Italian literature*

Introduction

Italian travel writing on India occupies a marginal yet revealing position in the larger corpus of European Orientalist literature. Guido Gustavo Gozzano (1883–1916), best known as a *Crepuscolare* poet, traveled to India in 1912–13 partly for health reasons and partly under journalistic commission. His journey produced a series of articles later collected in *Verso la cuna del mondo: Lettere dall'India* (1917). Although brief, this text offers important insight into how Italy without a colonial presence in India engaged imaginatively with the British Empire.

This article situates Gozzano's *Lettere* within the framework of Orientalist discourse and Italian literary culture. It argues that while the work is framed as first-hand observation, it

often functions as a mediated and imaginative construction of India, reliant on guidebooks, European accounts, and exotic tropes.

Gozzano's Journey and Observations

The travelogue begins in Bombay, where Gozzano notes the cosmopolitan port and the sign of colonialism in Bombay and comments (1917): “Tutto il porto dà il senso della schiavitù, ma non è un senso penoso: i dominatori sanno sfruttare l'uomo fino all'ultima energia, comandano con alterigia, ma con giustizia (Gozzano, 1917, p. 9)” [The whole port gives the sense of slavery, but it is not a painful sense: the rulers know how to exploit man to the point at the last energy, they command with pride, but with justice]¹. His subsequent itinerary—Goa, Ceylon, Madurai, Madras, Agra, Jaipur, Cawnpore, and Benares—follows a recognizable colonial circuit, though critics argue that parts of his journey may have been reconstructed through reading rather than experience.

Central to the text is Gozzano's perception of Anglomania: Indian elites adopting English habits, sports, and literature, often at the expense of indigenous traditions. He interprets this as evidence of admiration for the colonizers, suggesting that “Due cose sono care all'indiano: l'Inghilterra e la sua casta. “ L'India declina?...” – “Poco importa l'India, purché sia salva la fede”. – “Declina la fede...” – “Purché sia salva la casta...” È il dialogo approssimativo con ogni bramino ben pensante” (Gozzano, 1917, p. 83). [Two things are dear to the Indian: England and the caste. "Does India decline? ..." "India doesn't matter, as long as its faith is safe". – “Does the faith decline?” – “As long as the caste is safe...”. It is the usual dialogue with every good thinking Brahmin]. Such statements reveal both a fascination with and justification of colonial authority.

Eurocentric approach

Despite writing in the first person, Gozzano's India is often mediated by European sources and interlocutors. He frequently relies on Italians or other Europeans in India, such as Dr. Faraglia in Bombay, for explanations of local customs. Further, many critics such as Giuliana Benvenuti and Gaia de Pascale write that much of the material for the imaginative journey of Gozzano comes from Pierre Loti's *l'Inde (sans le Anglais)* [*India (Without the English)*], from Paolo Mantegazza, *l'India*, Jules Verne's *Casa a vapour* [*The Steam House*].

As discussed in the above section, it can be said that Gozzano's vision of India is imaginary and he derives information from the existing European literature. We can say that

¹ My translation

this travelogue is a journey on paper. The Orient for Gozzano is a place, which can be fantasized about. Gozzano tries to present an India, about which he has read in the newspapers, other travelogues and has seen through photos. Benvenuti (2008) in her book *Il viaggiatore come autore* writes that:

si fornisce in tal modo il credibile resoconto di un viaggio iniziato a Bombay e concluso a Benares, compiuto seguendo un itinerario coerente. Coerente, credibile, verosimile, ma non reale e tuttavia questo viaggio gozzaniano. E questo non solamente perché la costruzione del testo venne allestita a posteriori e in parte, ma anche perché — circostanza per molti aspetti sorprendente ma della quale oggi abbiamo certezza — molti dei luoghi che racconta Gozzano non li ha mai visitati. (Benvenuti, 2008, p. 68)

[Gozzano provides a credible account of a journey which began in Bombay and concluded in Benares, following a coherent, credible, true itinerary, but not real and yet this Gozzanian journey. And this not only because the construction of the text was prepared a posteriori and partly posthumously, but also because - circumstances for many surprising aspects of which today we are sure - many of the places that Gozzano writes about, he has never visited them]²

His language in the travelogue reveals a Eurocentric orientation: Indian names are transcribed in Italian phonetics, while English names retain proper spelling. English vocabulary, “bookseller,” “boy,” “native towns” appears untranslated, underscoring the dominance of colonial language. At times, Gozzano admits his inability to comprehend Indian spirituality, At one point in his travelogue, during a visit to a temple of Siva Lingam, he admits that; “ma è certo il mio cervello profano d’occidentale che non comprende l’occulto senso della pietra scolpita” (Gozzano, 1917, 14). [Certainly, my Western profane brain does not understand the occult sense of carved stone]. These gestures reinforce the cultural distance between observer and observed. Peter Hulme and Time Youngs in the Introduction of *The Cambridge Companion to Travel Writing* (2002) write that, “two particular modes of writing – forgery and

² My translation

its respectable cousin, parody – have especially close, even parasitic, relationships with travel writing since the lone traveller bearing far-fetched facts from remote climes offers the perfect alibi for the forger and a tempting target for the parodist” (5).

The travelogue of Gozzano uses Indian names as they sound in Italian. It shows the writer’s euro-centric approach to the Indian languages. For example, he writes: Pandjim, pankā, Imalaja, Haiderabat, Aurangseb, Giumma, Giajpur, Maraja Ge-Sing, Mirat and Pengjab. He writes a travelogue on India and writes the Indian names as per their pronunciation. Whereas British names although with alphabets which do not exist in Italian language have the correct spellings in the travelogue. For example, Lady Harver, Lady Sotten, Lady Wheeler, Miss Kraty and Hugh Wheeler etc. The language of the travelogue many times uses certain words in English without translating them into Italian such as bookseller, boy, native-towns, very comfortable etc. His use of English vocabulary seems to be presenting the colonial language and ambience of India. This also puts light on the influence of English over Indian languages during the British colonisation. This use of English seems to present the relation of domination over other local languages. Polezzi (2001) writes that in Gozzano’s case “a foreignizing strategy is used to distance the narrator and his target readers from the colonial reality portrayed” (Polezzi, 2001, p. 85).

Therefore, the question arises if these words are used consciously. A strategy that is planned, deliberate and goal-oriented to achieve a specific outcome. It shows the perceived relationship between the Orient and the west. Shela Burney (2012) in her article “Orientalism: The Making of the Other”, acknowledges that: “the origins of Orientalism were philological, which racialized the Oriental subject and endorsed a built-in sense of European superiority so that neither Macaulay nor Renan nor other Orientalists had any hesitation in denigrating the Oriental language, literature, culture, and religion as inferior. This is the power of empire and colonialism, as Said suggests, it can destroy the cultural identity, language, and land of the colonized Other through the practice and power of Orientalism” (Shehla, 2012, p. 39)

Conclusion

Guido Gozzano’s *Verso la cuna del mondo* exemplifies the complex interplay between travel, literature, and colonial discourse. Written by a poet rather than a colonial officer, the text nevertheless reproduces Orientalist stereotypes and legitimizes British authority. At the same time, it highlights Italy’s ambivalent position—simultaneously outside British colonial power yet complicit in its cultural representations.

The *Lettere* remain a valuable document, not for their ethnographic accuracy, but for the insight they provide into the imaginative construction of India in early twentieth-century

Italy. They demonstrate how even “minor” European voices contributed to shaping the literary Orient, reinforcing the nexus of exoticism, colonial power, and cultural identity.

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